

KO'RISH QOBILIYATI BUZILGAN BOLALARNI PSIXOLOGIK-PEDAGOGIK TEKSHIRISH.

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Annotatsiya. Ushbu maqolada ko'rish qobiliyati buzilgan bolalarni psixologik-pedagogik tekshirish haqida fikr yuritilgan.

Kalit so'zilar: afsona, Strabismus divergent, uzoqni ko'ra olmaslik, miyopiya.

PSYCHOLOGICAL-PEDAGOGICAL EXAMINATION OF CHILDREN WITH VISUAL IMPAIRMENT.

Abstract. This article reflects on the psychological and pedagogical examination of children with visual impairment.

Key words: myth, Strabismus divergent, farsightedness, myopia.

ПСИХОЛОГО-ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКОЕ ОБСЛЕДОВАНИЕ ДЕТЕЙ С НАРУШЕНИЯМИ ЗРЕНИЯ.

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматривается психолого-педагогическое обследование детей с нарушениями зрения.

Ключевые слова: миф, расходящееся косоглазие, дальнозоркость, близорукость.

Hatto qadimgi misrliklar ham o'zlarining afsonalarida ko'zni Quyosh bilan taqqoslashgan. Darhaqiqat, bizning ko'zlarimiz qimmatli va buyuk sovg'adir. Ularning yordami bilan biz atrofimizdagi hamma narsani ko'ramiz. Biroq, nafaqat yoshi bilan, balki odam ko'zlari bilan bog'liq muammolarga duch kelishi mumkin, ular allaqachon erta bolalik davrida bo'lishi mumkin. Shuning uchun ko'rish qobiliyati buzilgan bolalarni tashxislash imkon qadar tezroq amalga oshirilishi kerak. erta yosh (6 oydan boshlab). Ko'pincha oftalmolog strabismus bilan davolanadi. Bu xavfli, chunki u ko'rlikka olib kelishi mumkin (amblyopiya). Strabismus divergent (ko'zni ma'badga o'tkazganda) yoki konvergent (ko'zni burun ko'prigiga o'tkazganda) bo'lishi mumkin. Ko'zni ko'rishdagi farqlar bilan strabismus, shuningdek, o'zgaruvchan strabismus (bir yoki boshqa ko'z o'raganda), miyopiya (ko'z yaqindagi narsalarni yaxshi ko'rganda), uzoqni ko'ra olmaslik (ko'z uzoqni yaxshi ko'rganda), (har qanday holatda) mavjud. ko'zning yuzasi assimetrik), keyin mavzuning ba'zi qismlarining tasvirlari aniq, boshqalari esa loyqa.

Bola hali juda yosh bo'lsa, optometrist bilvosita ko'rishni tekshiradi. Chaqaloq ota-onaning qo'lida, shifokor unga ikki yarmiga bo'lingan plastinkani ko'rsatadi. Ulardan biri bo'sh, ikkinchisida esa chiziqlar bor. Ushbu usulning mohiyati shundaki, bola o'z nigohini planshetning bo'sh qismiga emas, balki chiziqli qismiga qaratadi. Keyin shifokor keyingi jadvalni ko'rsatadi, unda chiziqlar qalinligi kamroq bo'ladi, keyin esa - chiziqlar qalinligi undan ham kichikroq bo'lgan jadvallar va shunga o'xshash kichkina bemorning ko'zi chiziqlarni fondan ajrata olmaguncha. Ikkala ko'z ham navbat bilan tekshiriladi. Bundan tashqari, bir ko'zni tekshirganda, ikkinchisini yopish kerak. Bunday tadqiqot natijalariga ko'ra, bolaning ikkala ko'zi bilan yaxshi ko'rishi va ko'rish uning yoshiga mos kelishini tekshirish mumkin.

Farzandingiz 2-3 yoshga to'lganda, siz unga uyda oddiy testni taklif qilishingiz mumkin. Masalan, qog'oz varag'ida turli o'lchamdagi bo'yalmagan barglari bo'lgan daraxtni, derazali uyni va hokazolarni chizing. Keyin bolaning barcha barglarini, uydagi derazalarni va hokazolarni

ko'rishini so'rang va qo'lda chizilgan tafsilotlarni ko'rsatishni so'rang. Ko'zlarni birma-bir tekshirish kerak. Agar u rasmdagi barcha narsalarni ajratib tursa, u yaxshi ko'rish qobiliyatiga ega. Agar u rasmga 20 sm dan yaqinroq yaqinlashsa, bu allaqachon shifokorni ko'rish uchun signaldir.

Maktabgacha yoshdagi bolalarda ko'rish keskinligini tekshirish uchun ko'z shifokori kabinetlarida bola allaqachon biladigan narsalar chizilgan jadvallardan foydalaniladi. Rasmlar qatorlarga joylashtirilgan va o'lchamlari bo'yicha farqlanadi. Bolaga bir ko'zini yumib (va u kaft ostida ochiq bo'lishi kerak) va boshqa ko'z bilan rasmlarga qarang va ularda ko'rsatilgan narsalarni nomlang. Xuddi shu narsa boshqa ko'z bilan amalga oshiriladi. Agar bola to'g'ri javob berishdan oldin ikkilansa, bu bir ko'zning boshqasidan zaifroq ekanligini ko'rsatishi mumkin.

Bolalarda miyopi yoki gipermetropiyani o'rganish uchun halqali stollardan (bo'shliqli halqalardan) foydalanish mumkin. Masofaviy ko'rishni (5 metrdan) o'rganish uchun bir-birining ichida joylashgan turli uchta halqali chizmalar qo'llaniladi. Har bir halqa ma'lum bir ko'rish keskinligiga mos keladi. Yaqindan ko'rishni (1 metrdan) o'rganish uchun qatorlarga joylashtirilgan halqali stol ham qo'llaniladi (har bir qatorda halqalarning ma'lum o'lchami mavjud). Ko'rish keskinligi ballari har bir qatordagi halqalarning chap tomonida keltirilgan.

Bolalarda astigmatizmni aniqlash uchun siz ularga chiziqlarning yorqin figurasi bilan sinovni taklif qilishingiz mumkin (quyosh nurlari kabi chizish, bir xil qalinlikdagi uzun va qisqa chiziqlarni almashtiring). 1 m masofadan turib, bu raqamga qarang, navbat bilan bir ko'zni, keyin ikkinchisini yoping. Agar bolada chizikli ko'rishning ravshanligida katta farqlar bo'lsa, bu ko'z shifokoriga murojaat qilish kerakligini ko'rsatadi.

Boladagi ma'lum bir ko'z kasalligini o'z vaqtida aniqlash uchun siz uning ko'rish qobiliyatini muntazam ravishda tekshirishingiz kerak. Agar kerak bo'lsa, shifokor davolanishni buyuradi. Ota-onalar diqqat bilan qarashlari kerak to'g'ri tashkil etish bolalar uchun o'yinlar, tadbirlar va ishlar. Bularning barchasi bolada yaxshi ko'rishni saqlashga yordam beradi.

Ko'rish organini o'rganish tom ma'noda bemorga birinchi qarashdan boshlanadi. Yurish (noaniq yoki qoqilish), tananing holati (boshni pastga tushirish yoki orqaga tashlash, qo'llarni oldinga cho'zish), yopiq ko'zlar va boshqalar kabi tafsilotlar vizual funktsiyaning buzilishi haqida gapirish mumkin.

Shifokor bemorning shikoyatlarini aniqlab, ko'rish buzilishi tashxisini boshlaydi. Ba'zida dastlabki tashxis qo'yish uchun o'ziga xos, xarakterli alomatlarini aytish kifoya. Kasallikning aniqroq ta'rifi uchun qo'shimcha ravishda maxsus tadqiqotlar talab qilinadi.

Ko'rish buzilishi uchun ko'zni tekshirish usullari

Zamonaviy oftalmologiyada diagnostika maqsadida quyidagilar qo'llaniladi:

- tashqi tekshiruv;
- lateral yoritish usuli bilan o'rganish;
- uzatilgan nurni tekshirish usuli;
- oftalmoskopiya;
- avtorefraktometriya;
- biomikroskopiya;
- gonioskopiya;
- eko-oftalmografiya;
- retinaning floresan angiografiyasi va boshqalar.

Bolalarda ko'rish buzilishini tashxislash xususiyatlari

Bolalarda ko'rish organini tekshirish ham ko'zning holatini vizual baholash bilan boshlanadi.

- Uch yoshgacha bo'lgan bolaning oftalmologik tekshiruv uchun yordamchi kerak.

- Tadqiqotning maksimal aniqligini ta'minlash uchun bolaning boshini, oyoqlarini va qo'llarini ma'lum bir holatda mahkamlash kerak.

- Bolalarda ko'rish buzilishini tashxislash usullari kattalardagi kabi. Bundan tashqari, ko'z qopqog'ini ko'taruvchi kabi yordamchi vositalardan foydalanish mumkin.

- Ko'rish keskinligini aniqlash uchun ob'ektlar va hayvonlar tasvirlangan maxsus bolalar jadvallari qo'llaniladi.

Ko'rish qobiliyati buzilgan bolalarda diagnostika pediatrik oftalmolog tomonidan amalga oshirilishi kerak maxsus trening. Shu bilan birga, xususiyatlarni hisobga olish kerak asab tizimi bola, uning ko'zlarini uzoq vaqt davomida ma'lum bir ob'ektga qarata olmaslik, harakatchanlik va qo'zg'aluvchanlikni oshirish. Bundan tashqari, bolalarda vizual funktsiyalardagi o'zgarishlar psixo-emotsional holat, charchoq va umumiy buzuqlik bilan bog'liq. Shuning uchun, xato va noto'g'ri tashxis qo'ymaslik uchun, tekshiruv vaqtida bolaning nisbatan xotirjam, yaxshi ovqatlanishi, dam olishi va yaxshi kayfiyatda bo'lishi juda muhimdir.

Maktabgacha yoshdagi ko'rish qobiliyati buzilgan bolalarning psixologik-pedagogik diagnostikasining xususiyatlari.

Yuqorida ta'kidlab o'tilganidek, maktabgacha yoshdagi davrning tanqidiyligi odatdagi bolalarni ko'rishdan farqini anglash bilan tavsiflanishi mumkin.

Ko'rsatilgan tanqidiy davrlarga muvofiq, ko'rish qobiliyati buzilgan bolalarni tekshirish yo'nalishlari ham belgilanadi.

Odamning bolalarni oddiy ko'rishdan farqini anglash davri, maktabgacha yoshda o'z nuqsonlarini boshdan kechirish muammosi bolaning o'zini, uning shaxsiyatini, o'zini o'ziga xos, odatdagi bolalardan farqli ekanligini tushunishi va anglashi bilan bog'liq; aloqa va aloqalarni o'rnatishga, vizual idrok asosida bir qator harakatlarni amalga oshirishga qodir emasligini tushunish. Bu esa bolalarning o'zidan noroziligini his qiladi. Shu sababli, tekshiruvning birinchi yo'nalishi - bolaning o'z ehtiyojlari va xususiyatlariga ega bo'lgan shaxs sifatida o'zini bilishi yoki yo'qligini aniqlash.

O'z nuqsoni yoki kamchiligini tushunish va uni tuzatish zarurligini anglash o'z-o'zini tartibga solish harakatlarining paydo bo'lishiga yordam beradi. Shu bilan birga, o'zboshimchalik bilan etarli darajada shakllanmagan aqliy jarayonlar ko'rish qobiliyati zaif bolada atrof-muhitga nisbatan passiv pozitsiyaning paydo bo'lishi o'z-o'zini tartibga solish jarayonini murakkablashtiradi va sekinlashtiradi.

O'z-o'zini tartibga solish imkoniyati darajasi va darajasini aniqlash uchun quyidagilarni aniqlash kerak: bolaning his-tuyg'ularini bilishi.

Bu bilimlar shaxsning shaxsiy sinovlari, jismoniy sifatlarini, harakat qobiliyatlarini tekshirish va bolaga nimani yoqtirishini yoki yoqtirmasligini, nima qila olishini yoki qila olmasligini tushunish asosida shakllanadi;

ko'zoynak taqishning afzalliklarini tushunish;

davolash, hatto okklyuzyon yordamida ham;

ko'rishni rivojlantirish uchun maxsus sinflar;

zarur faoliyatni ko'rish va amalga oshirishga yordam beradigan qurilmalar;

O'yinlar, tadbirlar, dam olish uchun shaxsiy joyingizni tashkil qilish zarurligini tushunish; tanlangan bolalar va kattalar bilan muloqot qilish, o'zlarining shaxsiy muhitini yaratish istagi; shaxsiy maydon;

Zarur bo'lganda aniq vaqtda yordam so'rash imkoniyatini tushunish; ularning tashqi ko'rinishiga va boshqalarning ko'rinishiga qiziqishning paydo bo'lishi, uni baholash qobiliyati;

ko'zoynak taqish zarurligiga munosabat, ularning ko'zlarini ko'rish; turli sharoitlarda talab qilinadigan kiyimlarni farqlash: kortda o'ynash, tashrif buyurish uchun sayohat, uy atrofida yordam berish uchun jismoniy tarbiya va boshqalar; xulq-atvor ustidan o'z-o'zini nazorat qilishni amalga oshirish, ba'zi vaziyatlarda o'z xatti-harakatlarining nomuvofiqligini tushunish va kattalar yordami bilan jamiyat uchun to'g'ri va maqbul xatti-harakatlar shakllarini rivojlantirish istagi.

Ikkinchi yo'nalish ko'rish qobiliyati buzilgan maktabgacha yoshdagi bolaning ijtimoiy moslashuvining o'ziga xos muammolari bilan bog'liq. Bu bolaning jamiyatda yashashiga, yuzaga keladigan nizolar va qiyinchiliklarni kattalar yordamida ham, mustaqil ravishda hal qilishga yordam beradigan ko'nikma va fazilatlarining mavjudligi va rivojlanishini nazarda tutadi. Buning uchun psixolog quyidagilarni bilishi kerak:

Bolada jamiyat, boshqa odamlar, atrof-muhit haqidagi bilim va g'oyalarni kengaytirish jarayoni qanday rivojlanadi.

U odamlar va atrof-muhit bilan uchrashganda idrokning polisensor xususiyatidan qanday foydalanadi, yangi ob'ektlar bilan uchrashishdan qo'rqadimi;

u boshqa odamlardan qanday ma'lumot oladi va undan foydalanadi;

U odamlar bilan muloqot qilishdan qo'rqadimi?

U qarindoshlari va do'stlarining tor doirasiga yopishadimi; h

yangi ma'lumot olish uchun savol beradimi yoki yangi bilimlarni o'zlashtirishda passivmi;

U ko'rish qobiliyatining buzilishi bilan cheklangan axborot olish vositalarining o'ziga xos tizimini yaratadimi;

U atrof-muhitdan, odamlardan foydalanish ko'nikmalariga egami;

U o'z yordamini boshqa bolalar va kattalarga taklif qiladimi;

Ishtirok etish uchun buni tushunadimi umumiy sabab bolalar va kattalar jamoasi bilan tegishli xulq-atvor, ishtirokchilarni hurmat qilish va ijtimoiy qoidalarga bo'ysunish talab qilinadi (masalan, navbatda kutish, materiallar, o'yinchoqlar va boshqalarni bo'lishish);

ko'rish keskinligi va davolanish davridan qat'i nazar, odamlar bilan ko'z bilan aloqa qiladi;

Oiladan tashqaridagi odamlarga qiziqish bormi, u qo'shnilarga qiziqadimi, ular bilan aloqada bo'ladimi;

· do'stlarini faqat nomidan emas, balki ovozi, yurishi, kiyimi, bo'yi va faqat ularga xos bo'lgan individual fazilatlaridan taniydimi.

Uchinchi yo'nalish bilim, ko'nikma va psixologik tayyorgarlikni rivojlantirish zarurati bilan bog'liq bo'lib, tor jamoadan tashqariga chiqish va odamlar va jamiyat bilan aloqalarni kengaytirish, yangi odamlar, notanish makon qo'rquvini engish. Psixolog bolalarda jamiyat, ijtimoiy xizmatlar, zamonaviy texnologiya yutuqlaridan foydalanish qobiliyati va boshqalar haqida g'oyalarni ochib beradi.

Bolalarni kuzatish va tekshirishda quyidagilarga e'tibor berish kerak:

Bolaning jamiyat haqidagi tushunchasi kengayadimi?

U qanday ijtimoiy institutlarni biladi. Siz ularning vazifalari (pochta bo'limi, do'kon, klinika, novvoyxona, metro, bank va boshqalar) bilan tanishmisiz;

Ba'zi kasblarni (hamshira, o't o'chiruvchi, politsiyachi va h.k.) nomlab, tavsiflab bera olasizmi; bola onani, dadani, uydoshini og'zaki tasvirlab bera oladimi: qanday tashqi ko'rinish u kasbi bo'yicha kim, nima qiladi, ismi nima (to'liq ismi, otasining ismi va eng yaxshisi familiyasi, pul va undan foydalanish haqida nima biladi);

Vaqt va uning o'lchov birliklari (soat, daqiqa, ertalab, kechqurun, tun, kunduz, hafta, oy, yil) haqida tasavvurga egami;

u telefondan qanday foydalanishni biladimi, radio, televizor, magnitafon va boshqalarni yoqish / o'chirish texnik vositalar ma'lumot olish;

transport vositalarini (metro, taksi, trolleybus va boshqalar), ulardan foydalanish, yo'l haqini to'lashni biladi.

To'rtinchi yo'nalish:

§ mehnat faoliyatiga bo'lgan ehtiyojning shakllanishini aniqlash, ayniqsa ko'rishning chuqur buzilishida harakatlarni muvofiqlashtirish buzilganligi sababli ko'nikmalarni shakllantirish qiyin bo'lishi mumkin bo'lgan mehnat turlari uchun.

Bolani maktabga tayyorlash va o'tish davri. Ushbu davrda psixolog quyidagilarni aniqlashi kerak:

§ bolaning tayyorgarligi o'quv faoliyati;

§ bolaning oldingi davrda olgan bilim va ko'nikmalarini yangi sharoitda qo'llash qobiliyati;

§ o'quv faoliyati uchun motivatsiyani shakllantirish.

Bolani maktabga tayyorlash ko'plab asarlarda tasvirlangan. Ular orasida "Bolani maktabga tayyorlash" to'plamini alohida ajratib ko'rsatish mumkin. Unda berilgan testlar ko'rishda nuqsoni bo'lgan bolalarni quyidagi parametrlar bo'yicha moslashgandan keyin tekshirishda foydalanish mumkin:

§ topshiriqlarni bajarish vaqtini oshirish;

§ hajmini oshirish, tasvirlangan raqamlarning kontrasti;

§ yuklanmagan fon;

§ relyef konturlarini yoki barelef tasvirini chizish.

Muloqot bolaning jamoadagi va uning o'rnini belgilaydi shaxsiy rivojlanish. Ko'rish buzilishidagi aloqa jarayonlari jiddiy muammo bo'lib, uni hal qilish qiyin. Og'zaki bo'lmagan aloqa vositalarini bolalarda shakllantirish ayniqsa qiyin. Buning sabablari - inson idrokining tasvirining loyqaligi va normal ko'radiganlarning ekspressiv-mimik ifodalarini taqlid qilishning qiyinligi.

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